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Codicology and Palaeography: A relational model

Introduction

The systematic study of the basic characteristics comprising Greek and Latin manuscripts is organized along two main axes: first, understanding the nature of the physical object that holds what we perceive as writing; and second, studying the text itself, regardless of the complexity of such an endeavor. These two axes primarily concern the fields of Codicology and Palaeography.

The background of such a view is based on the assumption that before interpreting a text or applying any aesthetic or literary theory – fields largely attached to what we perceive as art – what comes first is the perspective of "material philology", which refer to the study of the materials used in the graphemic representation of a language. From the perspective of this article, the phrases "material text" or "materiality of the text" suggest an object-oriented view of the world, akin to the principles and methodology followed by the natural sciences.

In this context, Codicology and Palaeography are scientific fields that deal with the "archaeology of the storage medium"¹, a term we can use to describe any material medium that preserves text. Consequently, all codicological and paleographic features of a handwritten witness are treated as three-dimensional objects. To be more specific, they are viewed either as micro-3D objects (on the scale, for example, of a stroke observable by the human eye) or as macro-3D objects (on the scale, for example, of a marble structure Archaeology and Architecture are concerned with). Codicologists and paleographers, therefore, work at varying levels of detail – either microscopic or macroscopic – depending on the granularity required by their analysis when observing an object of interest.

Infrastructure

The aforementioned approach necessitates an accurate description and modeling of a handwritten witness, which humans perceive as a continuant² bearing traces of occurrences³. This involves listing, classifying, and elucidating all codicological and paleographical entities that comprise a handwritten witness, along with any additional information retrieved, such as details about the person, tools, and techniques used. This process is now strongly supported by methods that have been widely applied in other scientific fields over the last two decades; they include relational models that overcome the constraints imposed by typical, albeit complex, classifications. These models enable not only 'is-type' but also 'has-type' statements that describe corresponding relationships, as illustrated in the following example.

¹ Maniaci (2002: 16-19).

² Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 89).

³ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 121).

Image 1: Dashed lines illustrate "is-type" relationships, while solid line illustrate an "is-type" relationship.

Throughout any phase of creation and subsequent life of a handwritten witness, these two relationships persist for varying lengths of time, a duration that extends to the present of an observer. These relationships may be created, observed, or both by an agent, who acts either consciously (as in humans) or unconsciously⁴ (as occurs with insects and fungi) while participating in various processes. Such "agents" can be numerous and varied in their taxonomic classification.

At the present time, relational representations and models are dynamic – they are not merely static diagrams but machine-readable languages that facilitate logical inferences, a topic that will be discussed later –, supported by a theoretical infrastructure and technical applications known as "Top Level Ontologies". These ontologies⁵ are complex relational representations encompassing all possible detailed features of a domain, based on the principle that all fields of human action share common underlying principles. Practically speaking, Top Level Ontologies provide all basic classes ("is-type") and relationships ("has-type"), enabling the creation of additional classes and relationships as required by specific domains.

One of the most important and internationally recognized Top Level Ontologies is the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO), which recently (in November 2021) received an international standardization code (ISO)⁶. BFO enables the clear description of all entities associated with a handwritten witness; although a detailed description of all these entities is beyond the scope of this article, the basic entities that illustrate the relational view of Codicology and Palaeography and their constituents are described below.

Fundamental units and relationships

A fundamental assumption is that the entities comprising the domains of Codicology and Palaeography cannot be defined independently. These fields primarily focus on creating mostly aggregates of objects (a term that will be explained later) rather than individual objects. This approach necessitates a reconsideration of their content within the context of a complex system of relationships, a system that encompasses two basic categories of entities: fundamental units and the relationships that govern these units.

Object, object aggregate, fiat object part, and fundamental relationships

The basic categories of entities, upon which fundamental relationships are created and

⁴ "Conscious" (or "animate") actors, as opposed to "unconscious" (or "inanimate") ones, evoke obsolete classifications that should generally be avoided within a strict relational model.

⁵ Guarino (2009: 1-2); Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 1-4).

⁶ Developed over two decades, the methodology is detailed in the seminal work by Arp, R., Smith, B. & Spear, A. D. (2015). *Building Ontologies with Basic Formal Ontology*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press.

realized, include objects⁷, object aggregates⁸, and the so-called fiat object parts⁹.

Object

An object is considered an independent continuant that exists and persists through time, defined by discrete physical boundaries and acting as a bearer of properties, as well as of one or more roles¹⁰.

Image 2: Folding a sheet, a material object.

All major components used in codex construction are considered objects. This includes the physical materials¹¹ (such as papyrus, parchment, fabric- or wood-based paper) which are processed to create a ready-to-write substrate; often these materials are empirically named after the substance from which they are made. Objects also include the tools used for various tasks: folding a sheet to create a bifolium, ruling and pricking a substrate, incising, writing, and decorating, as well as sewing and gluing bifolia and independent leaves to create quires¹². Furthermore, an object can also refer to a human being, viewed as an independent individual with specific physical characteristics, bearing properties, and playing distinct roles in various processes. The following image taxonomically classifies some of the aforementioned objects, thus establishing "is-type" relationships.

Image 3: An "is-type" classification of objects observed in a codex.

For a codicologist or palaeographer, the general principle governing this classification is based on the assumption that these objects are considered units – fundamental entities – that, when combined, form larger sets governed by specific relationships. These sets, formally defined by BFO as object aggregates, are subsequently analyzed.

Object aggregate

We define an object aggregate as a set formed by objects that, while retaining their basic physical properties, form new entities with additional properties when aggregated over time following specific relationships (the concept of time will be further analyzed subsequently). Typical examples of object aggregates¹³ include an artificial bifolium, a codex, or a papyrus scroll, as depicted in the following images.

⁷ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 91).

⁸ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 93).

⁹ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 93-94).

¹⁰ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 96-101).

¹¹ Maniaci (1996: 19, 25, 41); Maniaci (2002: 39); Agati (2010: 58, 64,83).

¹² Gumbert (2010 draft: 1-9); Maniaci (2002: 58-61); Muzerelle (1985: 177-178).

¹³ The distinction between objects and object aggregates depends on the granularity one chooses to relationally describe a domain of expertise.

Images 4 and 5: "Has-type" relationships extend beyond simple taxonomies by connecting objects and object aggregates.

Images 6 and 7 (from left to right): The first image illustrates an example of an object aggregate; it depicts a quire consisting of various objects, including a natural bifolium, an independent leaf, and an artificial trifolium, which results from sewing an independent leaf onto a natural bifolium¹⁴. The second image illustrates the methods used to conjoin the individual objects into an aggregate, such as simple folding, using a stub, a guard, sewing without a guard, and sewing with a guard¹⁵.

Similarly, in the field of Palaeography, the fundamental unit (object) is considered to be the stroke¹⁶, which comprises the continuous trace perceived by the human eye, arising from the intentional arrangement of 'solid ink rocks' (in the case of soft substrates) present at a specific temporal instant on and within the internal cavities of a three-dimensional "spongy substrate" made of papyrus, parchment, or paper¹⁷. Over a defined temporal interval, the initially liquid ink quantities shrink as they solidify, due to physical phenomena, ultimately occupying only part of the cavities they initially filled. Such descriptions can be constantly modified, as the observer may choose varying degrees of granularity to describe events within a given unit of time.

It is also evident that concepts such as letters, punctuation marks¹⁸, and other symbols may require more than one stroke and are thus perceived as stroke aggregates. The capital Greek and Latin scripts from various periods, including *quadrata*, *rustica*, and *uncialis*¹⁹ are typical examples of this.

Image 8: a) An example of stroke aggregate in *rustica* script; b) the relational definition of a stroke aggregate²⁰.

Fiat object part

On the contrary, entities that are pertinent to both Codicology and Palaeography cannot be fully understood without acknowledging the existence of fiat object parts; these are a type of inherent objects that are neither objects nor object aggregates.

¹⁴ Maniaci (1996: 137).

¹⁵ Gumbert (2010 draft: 3.2).

¹⁶ Benetos, Papadaki, et al. (2024: 232-234).

¹⁷ Stroke variants in hard substrates such as marble and rocks also fall within the same relational model described here; however, further analysis of these variants goes beyond the scope of the present article.

¹⁸ Parkes (2016: 301-307); Clemens, Graham (2007: 83-85).

¹⁹ Petrucci (1992: 51-55, 64-67).

²⁰ Vaticanus Latinus 3867 f. 3v, lin. 1 (https://digi.vatlib.it/view/MSS_Vat.lat.3867).

A natural bifolium – resulting from the folding of a sheet – consists of two dependent leaves; however, integral to this bifolium are the furrow and the ridge that form during folding. To a human observer, the furrow and the ridge represent two aspects of the same area of interest, together constituting a crease (which serves as a hinge), facilitating the understanding of complex phenomena such as the movement when opening and closing a bifolium. Nonetheless, it is not entirely accurate to classify a crease and its constituent parts as either objects or object aggregates; instead, it is more appropriate to recognize the crease as a fiat object part of the bifolium, with the furrow and the ridge being fiat object parts of the crease itself.

Image 9: A dependent leaf as a fiat object part of a natural bifolium.

Similarly, ruling generates fiat object parts; however, these do not constitute a crease. This implies that a furrow – or the ridge on the verso side – can serve as fiat object part for two different objects. Such an observation provides a compelling argument for the superiority of a relational model over traditional taxonomies.

Images 10 and 11 (from left to right): In the first image, a bifolium features a crease as a fiat object part, which in turn implies the presence of a furrow and a ridge as its fiat object parts. In the second image, an independent leaf has undergone ruling on one side, leading the observer to recognize that it has both a furrow and a ridge as fiat object parts.

In Palaeography, the fiat object parts of a long stroke form the basis for cursive writing²¹, providing crucial insights into complex concepts such as the *ductus*²². This setup allows the stroke, the fiat stroke part, and the stroke aggregate to serve as the material basis upon which a human observer can engage in more complex processes, such as text recognition per unit of time and the nearly simultaneous transcription. In these processes, all three aforementioned categories – stroke, fiat stroke part, and stroke aggregate – participate as independent, material entities.

Image 12: Stroke and fiat stroke part.

²¹ Petrucci (1992: 61-63).

²² Petrucci (1992: 21).

Site

Perforations, gaps, tears, and other "modifications of the original material" are considered non-material entities because they are recognized by humans as areas of interest²³ that result from the removal rather than the creation of material objects. In the relational model proposed here, these entities are classified as "sites", as illustrated in the following.

Image 13: Topological regions (sites) of a handwritten witness.

Time and Process

As mentioned, Codicology and Paleography are distinct scientific fields, primarily distinguished by their fundamental units. However, both fields involve entities that participate in both codicological and paleographical processes²⁴. For instance, it is often the case that the same person is responsible for creating a bifolium and the text it contains, thereby assuming different roles over time. These factors – time and process – establish clear distinctions between Codicology and Paleography, providing researchers with a solid foundation for further development, as illustrated below.

Time

The creation of a writing medium is a complex process significantly influenced by time²⁵. This process begins at a specific moment, a temporal instant²⁶, considered the start of the "creation process", and ends at a defined point. Throughout this period, numerous individual moments occur, which are organized into durations of time as perceived by various observers, including scribes, parchment sellers, bookbinders, and others involved in the process. Consequently, a linear perspective of time is evident in every process, marked by specific instants and durations that a contemporary observer recognizes as distinct milestones. These milestones offer insights into entities that no longer exist, such as scribes and hands (manus)²⁷.

²³ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 110-113); Smith, Varzi (2002: 140).

²⁴ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 121-122).

²⁵ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 124-125).

²⁶ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 125).

²⁷ Duval (2015: 186, 236).

Image14: Time (temporal region) in relation to temporal instants and time durations (temporal interval).

The folding of a parchment sheet both begins and ends at specific instants, lasting for a defined interval. Similarly, in Palaeography and Textual Criticism²⁸, the terms *post* and *ante correctionem* suggest that it is possible to draw conclusions about specific temporal instants and intervals from certain topological areas (sites). In the image below²⁹, the site identified as *supra lineam* (that is, in the interlinear space) prompts the observer to make logical inferences based on time linearity, as there are three distinct temporal durations observed: initially, objects (and their corresponding object aggregates) are created "in row" (*in linea*); following this, objects created "above" (*supra lineam*) likely emerge in two separate temporal phases – the first includes the phrase *id est ocioribus*, and the second involves the insertion *-tio* along with the contemporaneous comma-like symbol located "below" (*sub linea*).

Image 15: Time as an essential container that transcends the limitations of space, as it can connect different sites within the same process.

It is impossible to determine the exact order of the mentioned temporal instants and intervals based solely on the manuscript's specific topology. Additional data, such as a larger excerpt of text, is required to establish another critical parameter: the observer's degree of certainty. This characteristic, along with other data properties³⁰, must be seriously considered in the relational model.

Image 16: Data properties, including the observer's certainty degree.

Process

Objects, object aggregates, sites, temporal instants, and temporal intervals are all part of the processes identified by the observer of a handwritten witness. Depending on the number of participants in a process, and the logical relationships that arise, the observer can reconstruct a range of processes. These range from simple ones – such as folding a full parchment sheet – to more complex ones, like transcription, which serves as the example that follows.

²⁸ Maniaci (1996: 241); Duval (2015: 100).

²⁹ Einsidlensis [lat.] 358(610) p. 151, lin. 21

(<https://www.e-codices.unifr.ch/en/sbe/0358/146/0/Sequence-1021>).

³⁰ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 156).

During the process conceptually known as transcription:

- A physical 3D object referred to as a "person" (or individual) assumes the role of "transcriber" for a specific time interval. This individual participates – with a certain degree of certainty – in any transcriptional unit during this process.
- A physical 3D object known as a "stroke", "stroke aggregate", or "fiat stroke part" is involved. This object is recognized as being present for a time instant or interval (depending on the granularity chosen by the transcriber) in a specific topological area (site) of interest.
- The distinctive footprint ("hand") of a person is engaged in a concurrent process called "recognition" during transcription. This process provides inferences about entities generally no longer existing (at least for historical handwritten witnesses) but are logically testified to have existed for a time period, such as "person" and "tool".
- An abstract entity, dependent on all the above, is conventionally referred to as a "transcriptional unit". This represents any Unicode character typed or any output of a typographical technique.

Conclusions

Considering the discussion above, two fundamental conclusions become evident.

Firstly, the necessity for a comprehensive relational model that integrates all entities related to Codicology, Palaeography, Stemmatics and Textual Criticism is paramount. A four-year research project at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens has culminated in the creation of the OHT Ontology³¹. This ontology has laid the groundwork for the Manuscribus digital platform – expected to be publicly available by the end of 2024 or early 2025. This platform is designed to significantly aid users in transcribing, annotating, and critically editing Greek and/or Latin manuscripts of their choice.

Secondly, there is an increasing need for robust, relationally described terminology that encompasses all components of the aforementioned domains. This need arises directly from the ontological relationships established by the OHT Ontology, prompting the creation of a new, relational dictionary.

In conclusion, I firmly believe that the fields mentioned must be updated in light of well-defined terms and definitions, supported by a strong, multidisciplinary theoretical model. Such updates will facilitate the development of serious digital applications that can transform a vast corpus of handwritten witnesses into structured data.

³¹ Initially, it was proposed to be named "OntoText Ontology", see Benetos, Papadaki, et al. (2024: 234); however, it was soon replaced by the current name OHT, which stands for "Ontology for Handwritten Text".

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